

LEXICOGRAPHIC INTERPRETATION OF MERONYMS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

Mustafaeva Sojida

Teacher of Termez State Engineering and Agrotechnology University

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Abstract. *The thesis analyzes how meronyms, one of the current word relationships in Uzbek and English, are given in dictionaries. Meronymy is a lexical-semantic relationship in which one word is used as a part of another word. In English, meronyms are clearly defined in dictionaries (e.g., under the term “...part of.” or “meronym”). However, in Uzbek dictionaries, these relationships are often explained only through definitions. The thesis compares these differences and suggests the need to present meronymic relations in Uzbek language dictionaries in a more systematic way. At the same time, the importance of integration of databases such as Pinceton WordNet in Uzbek lexicology is emphasized.*

Key words: *meronymy, holonymy, lexicography, lexicography, semantic relations, WordNet, lexical units*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tezisda o‘zbek va ingliz tillarida hozirgi so‘z munosabatlaridan biri bo‘lgan meronimlarning lug‘atlarda qanday berilishi tahlil qilinadi. Meronimiya – leksik-semantik munosabat bo‘lib, bir so‘z butunning qismi sifatida boshqa so‘zga nisbatan qo‘llaniladi. Ingliz tilida meronimlar lug‘atlarda aniq belgilangan holda (masalan, “....part of...” yoki “meronym” atamasi ostida) beriladi. Biroq, o‘zbek lug‘atlarida bu munosabatlar ko‘pincha faqat izohlar orqali tushuntiriladi. Tezisda ushbu farqlar taqqoslanib, meronimik munosabatlarni o‘zbek tilidagi lug‘atlarda yanada tizimli tarzda berish zarurligi taklif etiladi. Shu bilan birga, Pinceton WordNet kabi ma‘lumotlar bazalarining o‘zbek lug‘atshunosligida integratsiyasi muhimligi ta‘kidlanadi.*

Key words: *meronimiya, holonimiya, leksikografiya, lug‘atshunoslik, semantik munosabatlar, WordNet, leksik birliklar.*

The main goal of this study is to reveal the structure of expression of inter-word meronymic connection in dictionaries, and it is expected and concluded that the issues of interpretation of parts/pieces forming a hierarchical level under a single whole (superordinate) lexeme and their spiritual relations in lexicographic interpretations of both semantic essence and lexical content will be analyzed and concluded.

If we talk about lexical relations, we can say that the vocabulary of a language is not just a chaotic collection, but an ordered system - its components are represented as a system connected by lexical and semantic relations: hyponym-hyperonym, meronymy, holonymy, graduonymy, partonomical, synonymous, antonomic, polysemantic, etc. Formation of the computer linguistic base in all areas of modern linguistics, especially in the lexicographic world, which takes place on the basis of the expansion and development of new lexeme-meaning relations of the dictionary-lexicographic structure. Because, as I.R. Galperin wrote lexicography should include everything, it lives in a language that has not lost its power, value and ability to be used in speech, and also can reflect all new things that have been born, become viable and

stable in recent times. This once again proves that the growth of the language vocabulary takes place within the framework of new lexemes.

Meronymic relations of meaning serve the progressive growth of this vocabulary structural system. The Russian scientist Nikitin gives the following opinion about the above word-meaning relations: He mentions that the words “species-genus” and “whole-part” are recognized from them, which expand the entire dictionary system and are formed in a hierarchical system. This relationship is divided into two universal linguistic categories: hyper-hyponymy and meronymy. The study of the meronymic phenomenon is the main discursive issue of the current period, especially the full disclosure of their “secrets” is based on the further enrichment of the vocabulary system. Literally, until now, meronyms have been studied under the name of paronymy, which is closely related to holonymic - holo-meronymic and hyponymic meaning relationships. But today, the development of the lexical-structural system, its study as an individual meaning relationship was first raised by European linguists, and this later interested other linguists, especially our Uzbek linguists.

(B. Qilichev “Paronymy in Uzbek language”, A. Eshmo'minov “Creating a linguistic base of lexemes with taxonomic and meronymic relation for the corpora of the Uzbek language”) However, we hope that our research will answer some of the problems encountered in meronymic relations. Meronyms are referred to as “paronymy”, “paronym” or “part-whole” relationships in world lexicography, as we mentioned above. Meronymy is a lexical-semantic relationship in which one word is used in relation to another word that is part of a whole. For example: In Uzbek: “wheel” is part of “machine”. In English: “wheel” is part of “car”. Holonyms are the superordinate part that in English linguistics it can be the whole which are included the elements of meronym. For example; “machine” is the holonym of “wheel”, “engine”, “door” in Uzbek language, but in English “car” is the holonym of “wheel”, “engine”, “door”. So, it can be seen a bit difference between two language lexemes to express into variety descriptive words. However, the meaning of both them is similar as well as the functions.

Kroft and Kruz based on the meronymic relationship pattern “X IS – A- PART- OF Y” or “Y HAS- A Y”; S. Svorou interprets meronymic lexical relations as follows: [PORTION >PART-PIECE] portion (part/piece/portion) “the containment of one region or regions within another region” (One section of the city was blocked off); part(qism)” a portion characterized by self-sufficiency in that it has internal cohesion, and distinctness as an object (The kit includes all the parts to make a boat); piece(bolak)” an accidental portion with no definable relations to the whole other than origin” (There were several pieces of the boat found after the explosion), part-whole(Қисм-бутун)”relation is lexically relevant, so it can be seen that if meronyms express the lexical meaning between semantic relations, the whole-child relationship is a semantic relationship that is a set of elements that perceptually connect a certain essence individualized in existence.

Summary

The lexicographic presentation of meronyms in Uzbek and English languages has significant differences. In English, meronymic relations are clearly indicated in dictionaries, but in Uzbek they are mainly explained through annotations. Systems such as WordNet in English systematically link meronyms and show their interrelationships. In the Uzbek language, there is still no perfect system in this regard. In the future, defining meronymic relationships and creating semantic networks in Uzbek dictionaries will greatly contribute to the development of lexicology. This is especially important for the development of linguistics, lexicography

(lexicography) and linguistic corpus. Therefore, systematic classification of meronyms and their integration into dictionaries is one of the important tasks in the Uzbek language. It is important to show meronyms separately in Uzbek lexicology. Creating an Uzbek database like the English WordNet system contributes to the development of lexicology. Meronymic relations should be clearly indicated in medical, technical and biological dictionaries.

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